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LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOURS IN VIRTUAL TEAMS TO ACHIEVE PROJECT GOALS

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ABSTRACT

A systematic active learning leadership education programme for master's students has been implemented at the Graduate School of Engineering and Science since 2008. Leadership in this context refers to the skills that people can demonstrate at all levels, not just specific levels. After the spread of COVID-19 in the first semester of 2020, classes were remotely conducted. Project-based learning (PBL) activities used to practice leadership behaviour were also conducted in a virtual environment. In the PBL exercise, 17 teams tackled a variety of real-world issues related to local governments and businesses. The class for FY2020 focused on demonstrating leadership in achieving project goals with virtual teams. In the class, each team came up with ideas on accomplishing a project with virtual teams in terms of goal-achieving and team-maintaining behaviours. Based on these ideas, students set five rules for effective team management in the online version. Furthermore, for all team members to exercise leadership, each member identified their strengths and suggested to team members how they could contribute to the team activities. Finally, after confirming how to utilise the members' strengths to strengthen the team, students proceeded with the project. At the end of the project, the team showed increasing maturity in the team formation development stage. This paper reports on the content and results of specific discussions conducted in these classes to demonstrate leadership in achieving the project online.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Leadership education has been conducted for first-year students of the Master's programme at the Graduate School of Engineering and Science for over ten years[1] [2]. For FY2020, classes are forced to shift to online platforms to prevent the spread of COVID-19. In this regard, students form virtual teams and undergo project-based learning (PBL) [3] [4]. Learning is facilitated towards the formation of virtual teams to accomplish a project, where each member can demonstrate leadership[5]. The results of the survey confirm the improvement of the development stage of project team formation.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Leadership Class Overview

Leadership education was conducted in 2 out of 14 sessions. Students applied leadership training in a PBL exercise. The three goals of leadership education were as follows: (1) to understand the principles of leadership, (2) to understand the mechanisms of effective online communication and (3) to exercise leadership in a virtual team.

2.2 Education Method

Online communication tools, such as Zoom, learning management system and Google Drive were used. Figure 1 presents the design of the online leadership class. An instructor provided lectures to all students in the Main room. In addition, the students were divided into groups for discussion and collaborative work (Breakout room). Students were assigned to two rooms, namely, the Main and Breakout rooms, under the direction of the instructor.

Fig. 1. Online implementation environment

2.3 Class Contents

In the first class, the instructor provided a lecture to the entire group in the Main room. Students learned the advantages and disadvantages of virtual teams, team building, online communication and leadership skills required for the project. The students were then divided into 17 teams with 5–6 students per team. Students formulated ideas on accomplishing the project in terms of goal-achieving and team-maintaining behaviours. Table 1 presents an excerpt of the results of the group work.

Table 1. Ideas for accomplishing the project

Goal-achieving behaviours	Team-maintaining behaviours
Confirming objectives	Speaking in a polite manner
Sharing of understanding	Responding to members' opinions
Maintaining a strict time schedule	Understanding the amount of tasks of others
Identifying issues	Utilising videos for online meetings

In the second class, lectures were conducted to enable students to recognise their strengths and skills in their area of expertise and utilise them for the success of the project. Moreover, they learned about the importance of drawing on the strengths of team members. After the lecture, the students worked individually and in teams to identify their strengths and to share them with other team members. They listed specific possible actions and discussed how such strengths can be used to help one another successfully conduct the project. Table 2 shows an excerpt of the results of the group work.

Table 2. Ideas for leveraging members' strengths for project success

How to utilise the strengths of each member to enhance the team's capabilities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Identify skills that can be complemented by other members · Engage in tasks beyond one's strengths · Work with the awareness of exercising one's leadership · As a team, accomplish tasks that require a high level of skill, instead of designating such tasks to one member

2.4 Research Method

Using a 10-point scale, the students rated their team's stage of formation out of the four stages listed in the Tuckman model [6] (Table 3).

Table 3. Tuckman's team development model

Forming	Storming	Norming	Performing
Members lack knowledge of their roles.	A conflict in opinions and values occurs between members.	Team members examine effective processes for achieving goals.	Team members work together to achieve the goal.

If more than one stage was identified, then a numerical value was allocated and entered for each stage for a total of 10 points. Each person was evaluated once a week for six weeks.

3 RESULTS

The scores were summed for each stage per week for the 90 students to obtain a 100% stacked graph (Figure 2). A comparison of percentages by stage was then conducted. The forming stage continually decreased from 64.6% in the first week to 2.8% in the sixth week. The storming stage remained at 30% in the second, third and fourth weeks; however, it decreased to 19.5% by the fifth week and further to 8.0% by the sixth week. This indicates that it took a month to get through the storming stage. The proportions of the norming and performing stages increased per week. In the sixth week, the proportion of the performing stage exceeded that of the norming stage. The performing stage, which was 0.7% in the first week, eventually reached 51.8%.

Fig. 2. Virtual team development in online project-based learning

4 CONCLUSION

In the first semester of 2020, the study conducted online leadership education in observance of the social distancing required due to COVID-19. The PBL exercise, which was set up as a demonstration of leadership, was also conducted online. The students aimed to accomplish the project as part of virtual teams with awareness of the unique strengths of each member. The students evaluated the level of formation development of their team over a six-week period. The results confirmed the development of team formation over time.

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